

D1.5 Online EIC portfolio ecosystem database-second version

WP1: A systematic approach to expanding EIC portfolios into EIC deep-tech Communities

T1.2: EIC portfolio ecosystem analysis and database

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
<i>AI</i>	Artificial Intelligence
<i>BSOs</i>	Business Support Organizations
<i>CoPs</i>	Communities of Practice
<i>EIC</i>	European Innovation Council
<i>EU</i>	European Union
<i>FET</i>	Future and Emerging Technologies
<i>GDPR</i>	General Data Protection Regulation
<i>ICT</i>	Information and Communication Technology
<i>IPR</i>	Intellectual Property Rights
<i>PMs</i>	Programme Managers
<i>R&D</i>	Research and Development
<i>SMEs</i>	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
<i>TRL</i>	Technology Readiness Level

1. Introduction

This report, *D1.5 Online EIC Portfolio Ecosystem Database - Second Version*, builds on the initial methodology and findings presented in D1.4. The EIC Communities project aims to enhance the visibility and impact of European Innovation Council (EIC)-funded projects by fostering synergies and driving innovation breakthroughs. Central to this mission is the active selection, involvement, and engagement of **key stakeholders**, including scientific innovators, policymakers, and industry leaders.

The project focuses on creating three thematic Communities of Practice (CoPs) in the CleanTech, Industry, and Health sectors. These CoPs are designed to facilitate the co-creation of diverse online and physical activities, materials, and tools that promote multidisciplinary interactions among EIC selected projects. By collaborating closely with EIC representatives and Programme Managers (PMs), the project aims to pioneer new engagement practices and provide policy recommendations for the future of deep-tech research and innovation. Ultimately, the goal is to propel future technologies and innovations, fostering a more connected, innovative, and gender-inclusive deep tech community.

The purpose of this report is threefold:

1. Describe the updated methodology for identifying and analysing EIC projects selected for inclusion in the CoPs, as well as their associated ecosystem of stakeholders.
2. Report on the DEEPSYNC online databases by providing an updated list of EIC projects and stakeholders identified to date. The report covers also the latest analysis results.
3. Detail the exploitation strategies of the EIC projects, highlighting their needs and requirements to maximize impact and ensure successful commercialization and further research development.

The updated list of EIC projects and stakeholders identified to date are systematically organized into two interconnected databases: the EIC projects database and the stakeholder ecosystem database. These databases will be publicly accessible via the [DEEPSYNC platform](https://deepsync.eu)¹, powered by EIC Communities, serving as a valuable resource for broader engagement and utilization within the deep tech landscape.

This second version of the deliverable reports on the ongoing efforts to refine and expand the datasets. Future updates will continue this process, with the next release scheduled for February 2026.

The following document is organized as follows:

- **Chapter 1 - Introduction:** this chapter provides an overview of the EIC Communities project, its objectives, and the purpose of this deliverable as an update to the previous version.

¹ <https://deepsync.eu>

- **Chapter 2 - Methodology:** this chapter explains the updated methodology employed for the selection and assessment of projects, the identification and analysis of the stakeholder ecosystem, and the identification of the exploitation strategies of the selected projects. For a better understanding of this report, we also provide an update on changes that have occurred since D1.4 was submitted.
- **Chapter 3 - Assessment of Selected Projects:** this chapter details the criteria and processes used to evaluate the selected EIC projects, reports on the selected projects, and analyses their thematic alignment within the CoPs.
- **Chapter 4 - Stakeholder Ecosystem:** this chapter outlines the identification, profiling, and engagement of stakeholders, describing their roles and contributions to the CoPs and the overall project ecosystem.
- **Chapter 5 - Exploitation Survey Analysis:** this chapter presents the results of the exploitation strategies survey, highlighting the needs, requirements, and strategies for maximizing the impact and commercialization potential of the selected projects.
- **Chapter 6 - Conclusion:** this chapter summarizes the key findings and implications of the report, providing an outlook on future updates and the ongoing efforts to enhance the EIC portfolio ecosystem.

2. Methodology

In D1.4 online EIC portfolio ecosystem database -first version we laid out a three-step process to build the DEEPSYNC online databases:

1. Surveying EIC PMs to select EIC-funded projects and conducting desk research to evaluate them, analyse their exploitation strategies, and identify needs and challenges for future networking and synergies;
2. Identifying crucial stakeholders with a vested interest in CoPs and subsequently assessing them;
3. Compiling the gathered information into two distinct but closely connected databases that will be reflected on the DEEPSYNC platform.

The results of these steps are detailed in chapters 3, 4 and 5. Before delving into the current state-of-the-art of the DEEPSYNC online database, we provide an update on changes that have occurred since D1.4 was submitted.

2.1 Updates on the EIC projects online database and exploitation survey

In deliverable D1.4, the preliminary selection for the database included 90 Cleantech, 47 Industry, and 57 Health projects (total of 194). Since then, not all projects participated in the activities, and additional projects were selected for the Health CoP in collaboration with the EIC PM responsible for Medical imaging and AI in healthcare.

Consequently, the current online database comprises fewer projects than initially planned.

Chapter 3 will assess the current database and provide insights. Any future updates will be reported in D1.6 (M30), which will also offer more insights into exploitation strategies as not all projects have responded to the survey.

This report will also address gender distribution among EIC project representatives (data available only for project representatives who participated actively) but not the participation from widening countries due to initial selection constraints. As the projects were selected by EIC PMs, these numbers were from the beginning difficult to reflect in the composition within Communities and reach the target of 15% of actors from widening countries. However, efforts will be made to ensure broad representation through EIC project stories and selected speakers from widening countries, focusing on the coordinator's country of operation.

The [full list of projects is available on the DEEPSYNC platform](#), and they can be filtered by CoP, thematic area, women-led projects, and projects led by a coordinator established in a widening country, thus allowing for EU-wide outreach filtering.

2.2 Updates on the stakeholders' online database

Stakeholders identified at the proposal stage and reported in D1.4 were contacted through personal connections. The current methodology primarily involves direct mailing, with a communication strategy planned if more stakeholders are needed.

D1.5 will report on the numbers of all stakeholders, regardless of whether they are visible on the website or not. Therefore, it will report on those who have been contacted and are members of CoPs (but have not completed the survey) as well as those who have completed the survey and are now visible online. Only those stakeholders who completed the survey and gave consent are included in the online database due to GDPR regulation.

However, this report will analyze the stakeholders composition (gender, country, interest) only for those who are online, as they provided the necessary information for profiling.

The full list of stakeholders, that provided authorization to be published, is available on the DEEPSYNC platform, and they can be filtered by CoP and type of stakeholder.

3. Assessment of the selected projects

The selection and classification of projects for the three CoPs continued, especially with respect to those projects that were not identified and selected yet during the time the first version of this database was delivered (M4, December 2023). Since December 2023, the names of thematic areas for certain topics have changed (i.e., health and cleantech); this report also reflects those changes and, accordingly, the composition of projects per each community.

Compared to the initial selection, the number of shortlisted projects went down to 100 EIC projects, according to their active participation to the CoPs. The Cleantech community counts a total of 47 projects, followed by the Health community with 32 and Industry community with 21.

Figure 1: Number of projects per community

Delving into the EIC funding programs, 25 projects applied to the Accelerator, 55 to the Pathfinder, and 11 to the Transition program, 7 to FET and 2 to the SME Instrument. The breakdown below aims to provide insights into the diverse geographic representation of the selected projects, with Italy, Spain and France being the most represented countries across the three Communities.

Figure 2: Number of projects per country

The total amount of beneficiaries coming from widening countries is 11, which accounts for the 11% of the total.

[Figure 1: Number of projects per community](#)

3.1 Cleantech

Starting with the Cleantech community, a **total of 47 projects have been confirmed**. These projects are distributed across the following thematic areas: “Building materials”, “Energy solutions”, “Environmental preservation”, “Resilient agriculture”, “Renewable fuels”. The distribution of projects per thematic areas is represented in this chart:

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Figure 3: Number of Cleantech projects per thematic area

Examining the distribution of EIC beneficiaries per funding programme, 8 projects applied to the Transition, 9 to the Accelerator, and 24 to the Pathfinder program, 5 to FET and 1 to the SME Instrument.

Figure 4: Number of Cleantech projects per funding programme

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Finally, hereafter we also show the percentage of Cleantech projects per country.

Figure 5: Number of Cleantech projects per country

Another aspect that is important to emphasize, given the project's general objective of promoting good practices related to gender equality, is the current gender composition of the Cleantech CoP. During the community engagement session, held on February 27, a total of 51 project representatives participated actively. Among them, 20 were women (for more information, see *D2.4. Stakeholder engagement strategy in the Cleantech, Industry and Health CoPs*).

3.2 Industry

For the Industry thematic area, **a total of 21 projects have been confirmed and classified.** These projects are distributed across the following thematic areas: “Micro/nano-technologies”, “Space Tech & sustainability”, “Responsible AI”. The distribution of projects per thematic areas is represented in this chart:

Figure 6: Number of Industry projects per thematic area

Examining the distribution of EIC beneficiaries across funding programs, 5 projects applied to the Accelerator, 12 to the Pathfinder, 3 to the Transition program, 1 to FET and 0 projects from the SME Instruments programme.

Figure 7. Number of Industry projects per Funding Programme

Additionally, we include a breakdown showing the percentage of beneficiaries per country for a comprehensive understanding of the Industry CoP landscape.

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Figure 8: Number Industry projects per country

Regarding the gender composition of the Industry CoP, during the community engagement session, held on February 21, a total of 19 project representatives participated actively. Among them, 6 were women (for more information, see *D2.4. Stakeholder engagement strategy in the Cleantech, Industry and Health CoPs*).

3.3 Health

A total of 32 projects have been confirmed for the Health thematic area, from these 2 thematic areas: "Medical Imaging & AI", "Neurotech".

Figure 9: Number of Health projects per thematic area

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None of the projects has applied through the EIC Transition programme, 11 applied through the EIC Accelerator, 19 through the EIC Pathfinder, 1 through FET and 1 through the SME Instrument.

Figure 10: Number of Health projects per Funding Programme

Finally, we present the overall distribution of projects per country:

Figure 11: Number of Health projects per country

Regarding the gender composition of the Health CoP, during the community engagement session, held on March 13, a total of 14 project representatives participated actively. Among them, 3 were women (for more information, see *D2.4. Stakeholder engagement strategy in the Cleantech, Industry and Health CoPs*).

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4. Stakeholders' ecosystem

In the EIC Communities project, stakeholders are entities interested in joining the CoPs for active participation, collaboration, or information exchange. Their engagement is crucial for the project's success.

A three-step approach was used to identify and analyse stakeholders:

- 1- **Stakeholder identification**, aiming at identifying the possible stakeholders interested in the CoPs;
- 2- **Stakeholder profiling**, aiming at investigating the characteristics of the identified stakeholders;
- 3- **Stakeholder invitation** to join the CoP, through a formal invitation letter.

The stakeholders (organizations) identified at the proposal stage (92) are detailed in the previous version of this deliverable, *D1.4 Online EIC Portfolio Ecosystem Database - First Version*. These 92 stakeholders were contacted by partners in the past months, to gauge their interest in being part of the DEEPSYNC database and EIC Communities activities. Currently, the DEEPSYNC online database contains contacts of 42 individuals from 28 organizations.

Besides these, EIC Communities has 6 additional stakeholders in its internal, not public, database; their profiles could not be assessed as they did not fill in the survey. Accordingly, they were not included in the DEEPSYNC online database.

The additional 28 stakeholders (organizations) were profiled through a survey. The mapping process will continue until the project's completion.

4.1 Stakeholder identification

The stakeholder identification process began by gathering input from the project's partners. Each partner pinpointed potential stakeholders for profiling and inclusion in the project. In this deliverable, only those stakeholders identified by the partners are considered. As the kick-off of the activities of EIC Communities CoPs, more stakeholders will be included.

Currently, the partners have surveyed 28 stakeholders (through their 42 representatives), which, combined with those who did not complete the survey brings the total to 34. If we add those mentioned in the initial proposal, the total number is 126.

Regarding the 28 stakeholders that have been contacted for profiling, results are summarized in the following chapter.

Table 1: Overview of identified stakeholders

Name of the Organization	Female Leadership	Type of Stakeholder	Geographical Origin and Scope	Sector	CoP of Interest
A2A	No	Corporates	Europe	Cleantech; Energy and Sustainability, Life Company	Cleantech; Industry
Bilişim Vadisi	No	R&D infrastructures facilities	Asia	Technological Development Zone which includes startups from all sectors	Industry
CSIL	Yes	Consulting companies	Europe	Consulting and research across multiple sectors (light industries, space and defence, ICT, construction)	Industry
CYRIC CYPRUS RESEARCH AND INNOVATION CENTER LTD	No	BSOs_incubators	Europe, Middle East, Asia	SECTOR AGNOSTIC INCUBATOR	Health; Cleantech; Industry
Civitta	No	Corporates	Europe	Various	Industry
CyRIC Cyprus Research and Innovation Centre Ltd	No	BSOs_incubators	Europe, Middle East, North America	Healthcare, Deep tech	Health, Cleantech
GRAVITY VC FUND	No	Investors	EUORPE, MIDDLE EAST, AFRICA	VARIOUS	Health; Cleantech; Industry
Galp	Yes	Corporates	Europe, Africa, South America	Energy; Oil&Gas	Cleantech
INAM	No	Public entities	Europe, Asia, North America	Company-building; incubation, acceleration, technology	Industry

				strategy, innovation	
INEGI	No	Universities & research centers	Europe	R&D - Industry	Industry
InnovhubSSI	No	Universities and research centers	Europe	Applied Research	Cleantech; Industry
International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory	Yes	R&D infrastructures facilities	Europe	Research and Technology Organisation	Health; Cleantech; Industry
Istituto Oncologico Veneto	Yes	Hospital and medical centers	Europe	Health	Health
Madrid Science Park	Yes	Universities and research centers	Europe	Life sciences, health, medtech, sustainable chemistry, ITCs-digital technologies.	Health; Cleantech; Industry
Namlab gGmbH	No	Universities and research centers	Europe	Micro- and Nanoelectronics	Industry
RAIZ, The Navigator Company	No	R&D infrastructures facilities	Portugal and World	Forest, Bioeconomy and Bioproducts, Paper and Pulp	Industry
SFS Group	Yes	Corporates	Europe, Asia, North America, South America	Construction	Industry; Cleantech
SpaceFounders	No	BSOs_incubators	Europe	Space (Up- & Downstream)	Cleantech; Industry
SpaceFounders France	Yes	BSOs_incubators	Europe	Space	Industry
Technoport	Yes	BSOs_incubators	Europe, Africa, Asia	Deeptech sectors	Health; Cleantech; Industry

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University of Cagliari	No	Universities and research centers	Europe	Research	Health
University of Foggia	No	Universities and research centers	Europe	Research	Health; Cleantech; Industry
University of Salento	No	Universities and research centers	Europe	Public Research	Health; Cleantech; Industry
University of Udine	No	Universities and research centers	Europe	Academic; Research	Industry; Cleantech; Health;
Università Vita-Salute San Raffaele	No	Universities and research centers	Europe	Health	Health; Industry
Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro	Yes	Universities and research centers	Europe	Research	Health; Industry
WLOUNGE	Yes	Consulting companies	Europe	IMPACT INVESTMENT / SUSTAINABILITY, MEDICAL, FINANCE	Health; Cleantech
Istituto zooprofilattico sperimentale del Lazio e della Toscana	No	Universities and research centers	Europe	agriculture; health	Cleantech

4.2 Stakeholder profiling

Within the 28 stakeholders surveyed, there is a significant representation of female leadership. The chart shows that 36% of the organizations are led by females, which highlights a substantial presence but also underscores that the majority, 64%, are led by non-female leadership. Women lead in various sectors including corporates, universities and research centers, business support organizations and incubators, R&D infrastructures, and medical centers.

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Figure 12: Women-led organizations/initiatives

Figure 13: Type of organisations

The bar graph reflects the diverse organizational involvement in the EIC Communities project, highlighting the prominent role of **universities and research centers**. This aligns with the project's goal of fostering interdisciplinary collaborations within CoPs. The significant representation of corporates and **BSOs_incubators** underscores the multidisciplinary approach, crucial for co-developing innovative practices and policies. Additionally, the presence of **R&D infrastructures** and investors supports the project's comprehensive ecosystem, essential for both research and commercialization activities, ensuring the project's success across various sectors.

The geographical distribution of stakeholders within the EIC Communities project predominantly features a robust **European** engagement, accounting for 96% of the participants. This substantial presence highlights the project's integration within the EIC's objectives to enhance the visibility and impact of European-based technologies and innovations. Beyond Europe, the selected stakeholders maintain global connections, with **Asia** contributing 21% to the stakeholders' scope of action, reflecting significant involvement with the continent's burgeoning tech and innovation sectors. Both **Africa and North America** are represented equally, each holding 14% of the stakeholders' share, indicating strategic partnerships that address regional technological and industrial needs. A smaller yet impactful range of actions of the mapped stakeholders includes **South America** and the **Middle East**, at 11% and 14% respectively. These figures collectively demonstrate the project's extensive international reach, designed to facilitate cross-regional collaboration and the exchange of knowledge across multiple technological domains.

Region	Percentage
Europe	96%
Asia	21%
Africa	14%
North America	14%
South America	11%
Middle East	14%

Figure 14: Geographical origin of mapped stakeholders

The pie chart illustrates the distribution of stakeholders' interests across the three thematic CoPs within the EIC Communities project. The largest segment of stakeholders, comprising 42%, shows a predominant interest in **Cleantech CoP**, reflecting a strong focus on environmental and sustainable technologies. This is followed closely by the **Industry CoP**, which captures the interest of 30% of the stakeholders, indicating a significant engagement with advances in industrial processes and technologies. **Health CoP**, representing 28% of the stakeholder interest, indicates a robust commitment to medical and health-related innovations. This distribution underscores the balanced yet distinct focus areas within the EIC Communities, highlighting the project's comprehensive approach to fostering innovation across key sectors critical to future technological and social advancements.

Figure 15: Stakeholders' interest in CoPs

4.3 Stakeholder invitation

Every profiled stakeholder was contacted. Project partners established contact by sending invitation letters to stakeholders identified during the proposal stage and in subsequent months. Each partner was directly responsible for reaching out to stakeholders based on prior collaborations, personal connections, and shared network memberships. Partners invited the profiled stakeholders to join the CoPs and become members of the EIC Communities' stakeholder database. Integration into the database only proceeded if the stakeholders expressed a willingness to be included, respecting their autonomy and ensuring active engagement. This approach ensured that the database remained a living and active resource.

5. Exploitation survey analysis

The EIC Communities project aims to expand its CoPs by systematically examining the growth trajectories outlined in the exploitation strategies of the selected projects. These strategies provide strategic frameworks, highlighting requirements and developmental pathways for both Communities and individual projects.

The analysis considers the exploitation strategies of the selected projects to understand each project's objectives, resources, and milestones within the CoP framework. This involves:

1. **Identification of the main typologies of Key Exploitable Results (KERs):** determining the main innovations developed by the projects.
2. **Identification of exploitation strategies:** outlining the strategies for exploiting the main KERs in the projects.
3. **Requirements assessment:** identifying key aspects to address the expansion of CoPs based on the identified exploitation strategies.

A survey designed for project coordinators has been shared among the mapped projects. This process will continue until the project's completion to reach more projects for inclusion in the CoPs. The following paragraphs outline the outcomes of the survey's analysis for each CoP.

5.1 Cleantech CoP

The following table summarizes the main projects mapped and analysed for the Cleantech CoP.

Table 2: Main projects mapped and analysed for the Cleantech CoP.

ID	Project acronym	Programme	Tematic/challenge	Thematic area	Organization name	Country
1	BABOTS	EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture	UNIVERSITE DE NAMUR ASBL	Belgium
2	Direct commercialization of a new product or service;	EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Building Materials	Fibrtech SP Zoo	Poland
3	SWARM	EIC Accelerator	Challenge	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture	SABI AGRI	France
4	H2STEEL	EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	-	Politecnico di Torino	Italy

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5	MeBattery	EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	-	University of Burgos	Spain
6	Nanowings	EIC Transition	Thematic	-	Linari Engineering	Italy
7	PLANKT-ON	EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	-	Enphos	Italy
8	ZERAF	EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	-	EURAC	Italy
9	NEMILIES	EIC Transition	Thematic	Energy Storage	Invisible-Light Labs GmbH	Austria

5.1.1 Identification of projects' KERs

Figure 16: KERs of the projects - Cleantech

As can be seen from the *Figure 16, KERs of the projects - Cleantech*, most of the projects focus on the development of "**Hardware technology**" and "**Process**" solutions. 9% was recorded for both "Advancement in Knowledge" and "Software and Algorithm" while all the other KERs collected 5%. From the pie chart below, it can be seen that 66.7% of the contacted projects consider protecting their results with a patent.

Figure 17: Projects that consider a patent to protect results (%)

5.1.2 Identification of exploitation strategies

Figure 18: Exploitation strategies

The main exploitation strategies anticipated by the mapped projects after their completion include:

- **TRL upscaling:** advancing the Technology Readiness Level of innovations to make them market ready.

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- **Direct marketing of the product or service:** implementing strategies to directly sell and promote the developed products or services.
- **Spin-offs, joint ventures, or startup launches:** creating new business entities or partnerships to commercialize project outcomes.

By dividing the response categories into two clusters, it is possible to observe how the exploitation strategies are equally divided between "Direct exploitation in the market" and "research oriented". Notably, within the research-oriented exploitation pathways, the "TRL upscaling through further research" has been selected many times, highlighting how, in many cases, further research is needed to upscale the results before approaching the market.

Figure 19: Exploitation strategies cluster

5.1.3 Requirements assessment

The mapped projects clearly articulate the need for diverse stakeholders to amplify their impact and facilitate expansion across various domains, highlighting the tailored requirements rooted in the specific outcomes and strategic visions for the exploitation of the results of each project. Notably, *Figure 20*, detailing the stakeholders needed for project exploitation, reveals that nearly half of the essential stakeholders are tied to **commercial exploitation**. This underscores a strong emphasis on **market entry** and the **commercialization of innovations**, where **industry partners, marketing experts, and distribution networks** play pivotal roles in transitioning from research to market presence.

Additionally, **financial resources** emerge as crucial, especially for projects that focus on **upscaling their TRL**. This is particularly true for hardware-oriented projects, which often

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require extended periods of research and technical development before they are market-ready. The financial imperative is highlighted by the significant need for stakeholders capable of providing substantial funding, such as **venture capitalists, investors, and financial institutions**. These financial backers are essential, given the long development timelines and high costs associated with advancing these innovations from the prototype stage through to testing, refinement, and ultimately, market deployment.

Figure 20: Stakeholder needed by projects for the exploitation

5.2 Industry

The following table summarizes the main projects mapped and analysed for the Industry CoP.

Table 3: Main projects mapped and analysed for the Industry CoP

ID	Project acronym	Programme	Tematic/challenge	Thematic area	Organization name	Country
1	ASTOUND	EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI	UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID	Spain
2	BAYFLEX	EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics	UNIVERSITE PARIS-SACLAY	France
3	FVLLMONTI	EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics	UNIVERSITE DE BORDEAUX	France

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4	GuestXR	EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI	FUNDACIO EURECAT	Spain
5	PRINGLE	EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics	UNIVERSITEIT ANTWERPEN	Belgium
6	ROBIOPSY	EIC Transition	Thematic	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI VERONA	Italy
7	Fibritech	EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Building Materials	Fibritech SP Zoo	Poland

5.2.1. Identification of project KERs

Figure 21: KERs of the projects – Industry

Figure 21, *KERs of the projects – Industry*, shows a predominant focus among projects on developing **"Hardware technology"** and **"Software and Algorithm"** solutions. The figure notes that 19% of projects emphasize **"Methodology,"** while other KERs collectively account for 6%. Remarkably, all projects within the Industry Community of Practice (CoP) plan to protect their results with patents, underscoring the strategic importance of intellectual property in these initiatives.

5.2.2. Identification of exploitation strategies

Figure 22: Exploitation strategies – Industry

The main exploitation strategies anticipated by the mapped projects after their completion include:

- **TRL upscaling:** advancing the Technology Readiness Level of innovations to make them market ready.
- **Licensing/transfer of IPR:** granting permission to use intellectual property rights in exchange for other forms of compensation
- **Direct marketing of the product or service:** implementing strategies to directly sell and promote the developed products or services.

The segmentation of responses into two clusters illustrates a stronger inclination toward commercialization over research, suggesting that over half of the outcomes are highly marketable. TRL upscaling also emerges as a crucial path, emphasizing the ongoing need for further research to enhance maturity levels.

Figure 23: Exploitation strategies clusters

5.2.3 Requirements assessment

Figure 24: Stakeholder needed by projects for the exploitation

The mapped projects have detailed the necessity for various aspects to maximize their impact and ensure expansion in the fields of stakeholders and resources needed.

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Figure 24- Stakeholder needed by projects for the exploitation, outlines the stakeholder roles crucial for maximizing the impact of projects and ensuring their expansion. This figure correlates strongly with the identified exploitation strategies and KERs, highlighting the integrated approach to project development.

Financial resources are critically needed for **TRL upscaling strategies**, especially as projects with higher TRLs often entail significant investment for additional research and technical advancements. This financial backing is essential to bring hardware and technology projects to a market-ready stage.

The data shows that 14% of necessary stakeholders are "**Technical experts**" and another 14% are "**Universities**," both crucial for advancing the technical development of project results. Given the focus on hardware technology (31%) and software and algorithms (25%), these experts provide the **specialized knowledge** required for further refining and developing these technologies.

Moreover, the role of **commercial partners** is also highlighted as being integral to the exploitation strategy, critical for introducing and scaling the market presence of developed products and services. Their involvement is key to **navigating market dynamics**, establishing distribution networks, and executing effective marketing strategies.

5.3 Health

The following table summarizes the main projects mapped and analysed for the Health CoP.

Table 4: Main projects mapped and analysed for the Health CoP.

ID	Project acronym	Programme	Tematic/challenge	Thematic area	Organization name	Country
1	B-CRATOS	EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	Neurotech	UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	Sweden
2	LUMINOUS	FET	Thematic	Neurotech	STARLAB BARCELONA SL	Spain
3	RISEUP	EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	Neurotech	AGENZIA NAZIONALE PER LE NUOVE TECNOLOGIE, L'ENERGIA E LO SVILUPPO ECONOMICO SOSTENIBILE	Italy
4	ROBIOPSY	EIC Transition	Thematic	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI VERONA	Italy

5.3.1. Identification of project KERs

Figure 25: KERs of the projects - Health

As can be seen from *Figure 25, KERs of the projects - Health*, most of the projects focus on the development of "**Software and Algorithm**", "**Advancement in knowledge**" and "**Hardware technology**". all other categories record 9%. All of the selected projects consider protecting their results with a patent.

5.3.2 Identification of exploitation strategies

Figure 26: Exploitation strategies – Health

The main exploitation strategies anticipated by the mapped projects after their completion include:

- **Research and scientific exploitation:** conducting further scientific studies to deepen knowledge or for academic purposes such as publishing articles
- **TRL upscaling:** advancing the Technology Readiness Level of innovations to make them market ready.
- **Direct marketing of the product or service:** implementing strategies to directly sell and promote the developed products or services.

The division of response categories into two clusters reveals a balanced approach between "Direct exploitation in the market" and "research-oriented" strategies. This split indicates that while half of the project results are immediately marketable, the remainder necessitates additional research to achieve a higher maturity level.

Figure 27: Exploitation strategies - Health

5.3.3. Requirements assessment

Figure 28: Stakeholder needed by projects for the exploitation - Health

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Figure 28, Stakeholder needed by projects for the exploitation - Health, elaborates on the stakeholder roles critical for amplifying the projects' impact and supporting their expansion. The graph correlates with the exploitation strategies and KERs, emphasizing an integrated approach to project development.

Public funding emerges as a pivotal element, especially for **TRL upscaling**, underscoring the essential role of financial backing in elevating technology readiness, particularly for hardware-driven projects which typically demand significant ongoing investment in R&D.

Commercial partners are identified as crucial for executing direct commercialization strategies. Their involvement is instrumental in facilitating the **introduction and scaling of products and services in the market**, helping to navigate market dynamics, establish distribution networks, and implement effective marketing strategies.

Furthermore, **technical experts** are highlighted as particularly vital, given their role in developing and refining hardware technologies and software algorithms. These experts are essential for ensuring that the technologies not only meet market demands but also comply with regulatory standards, thereby facilitating successful market entry and adoption.

6. Conclusions

This report, D1.5 Online EIC Portfolio Ecosystem Database – Second Version, serves as a continuation of the D1.4 Online EIC Portfolio Ecosystem Database – First Version. It details the results from the EIC Communities' refined methodology for the selection and assessment of selected EIC projects and their expansive ecosystem of stakeholders. Furthermore, this report updates the list of projects and stakeholders identified thus far by the project partners. It also provides a comprehensive analysis of the exploitation strategies forecasted or employed by these projects.

Building on D1.4, this report highlights the progress in the selection and classification of projects for the three CoPs, the identification of stakeholders, and the analysis of the selected projects' exploitation strategies. Key outcomes include:

- The online database on the [DEEPSYNC](#) platform counts a **total number of 100 projects** actively involved. These are detailed across the Cleantech community with 47 projects, the Health community with 32, and the Industry community with 21. These projects span various EIC funding programs, including the **Accelerator, Pathfinder, Transition, FET, and SME Instrument**, reflecting a broad spectrum of innovative endeavours aimed at addressing critical technological and societal challenges. Out of 100 selected projects within the EIC Communities, based on the participation in community engagement sessions, 29 are represented by women.
- The EIC Communities project has surveyed 28 **stakeholders** predominantly from Europe, along with significant representation from Asia, Africa, North America, South America, and the Middle East. Stakeholder interests span across three CoPs: Cleantech (42%), Industry (30%), and Health (28%), with a notable 36% of organizations led by women, reflecting the project's commitment to gender diversity and interdisciplinary collaboration.
- The online database on the DEEPSYNC platform counts a **total number of 42 stakeholders from 28 organizations. In total, 34 organizations and their representatives as actively involved in EIC Communities' project activities.**
- **The subsequent phases will continue to integrate and activate stakeholders**, enhancing the overall structure and effectiveness of the CoPs, and ensuring the project's objectives are met with wide-reaching impacts across Europe and beyond.
- The mapped **exploitation strategies** for the selected projects within the EIC Communities, mainly focus on TRL upscale to enhance market readiness, licensing intellectual property, and directly marketing products and services. This highlights projects' needs and requirements, including **securing financial resources, engaging technical experts, and forming commercial partnerships.**
- The outcomes of the exploitation analysis suggest that CoPs and communication efforts from project's partners must prioritize networking with **investors, technical experts, and industry partners**, and develop strategic communication plans to showcase projects' outcomes, ensuring effective commercialization and ongoing innovation.

A final report, D1.6 Online EIC Portfolio Ecosystem Database - Third Version, will be provided at M30, offering comprehensive details and the final update on all activities.

